

Moodle learning management system is the leading LMS for education

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Abstract

Nowadays it is not possible to think about the teaching and learning process without associating it with the Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs). Actually, ICTs are present in all processes that involve collection of data, processing of information and knowledge creation, being the teaching and learning one of the most typical processes having these characteristics. ICTs play an important role in education, having a special relevance in the instructional component, supported by Learning Management Systems (LMS), such as Moodle. However, these platforms have many capabilities provided that they are used in their fullness. For example, interaction, feedback, conversation and networking are some of the possible actions using learning platforms. Furthermore, they provide a lot of opportunities to explore new methods of teaching and learning. There are some studies that identify the Moodle (Modular Object-Oriented Dynamic Learning Environment) as the most used platform in higher education, as well as the most easy to use. Moodle (modular object-oriented dynamic learning environment) is a free e-learning software platform, originally developed to enable educators to create online courses to encourage interaction and collaborative construction of learning content. It provides several opportunities for the 'teacher' to transform from being 'the source of knowledge' to being a facilitator and role model in the process of acquiring knowledge and skills.

Keywords: Moodle, LMS

Introduction

Now-a-days, with the use of technology and the Internet, education is undergoing significant changes, contemplating new ways of teaching and learning. One of the widely methods of teaching used to promote knowledge, consists in the use of virtual environments available in various formats, taking as example the teaching-learning platforms, which are available online. The Internet access and use of Laptops have created the technological conditions for teachers and students can benefit from the diversity of online information, communication, collaboration and sharing with others. The integration of Internet services in the teaching practices can provide thematic, social and digital enrichment for the agents involved.

A Learning Management System (commonly abbreviated as LMS) is a software application for the administration, documentation, tracking, and reporting, classroom, and online events, e-learning programs, and training content. LMS range from systems for managing training and educational records to software for distributing online or blended/hybrid college courses over the Internet with features for online collaboration, school districts, and schools use LMSs to deliver online courses and augment on-campus courses.

LMSs also act to augment the lessons the teacher is giving in a brick and mortar environment, not just replace them. Corporate training departments use LMSs to deliver online training, as well as to automate record-keeping and employee registration. From the very basic "problem cylinder", "KHUT", "SAKI" to Microsoft's Sharepoint Learning Kit and the powerfully simple ProProfs LMS, this infographic tracks the incredible journey of Learning Management Systems since it began in 1906, when University of Wisconsin was established as the first distance

learning institution. The Learning Management System Timeline Infographic Learning Management System has come a long way since the 1950's to become an integral part of educational strategy today. Online learning has become more popular today, and Learning Management System (LMS) help to administer, document, report, deliver and track online training programs and education courses.

What LMS can do?

- Contains different modules
- Ability for students to communicate and collaborate
- Online assessment options with immediate feedback and grade posting
- Shows every aspect of a student's academic life
- Allows parents to view progress

Characteristics of Learning Management System

- Centralize administration
- Use self-service and self-guided methodologies
- Able assemble content rapidly
- Supports portability and standards
- Enables personalization of content

Popular Learning Management System

Blackboard/Angel learning

Blackboard's learning management system (LMS) solutions bring all of these components together so you can deliver a cost-effective and meaningful learning experience at all levels, for all users. Thought Blackboard (LMS), we can bring your classroom online. With tools to engage, collaborate, grade, track assignments and more, you can reach students effectively to ensure they are interacting with the content and curriculum in the most effective ways. Regardless of the environment, there are core components

of e-learning that enrich the learning process.

Haiku

Haiku LMS is a secure, learning management system that emphasizes content, creativity, and community. Teachers can create Haiku websites for each of their classes and can post information including assignments, quizzes, grades, and multi-media resources. Students and their parents will have access to that information as well as many other interactive features.

Moodle

Moodle that is the acronym for

- Modular
- Object-Oriented
- Dynamic
- Learning
- Environment

It’s an online Learning Management System (LMS)

Moodle is a free open-source learning management system, also known as Learning Management System (LMS) or a virtual learning environment (VLE). Moodle’s modular design makes it easy to create new courses, adding content that will engage learners. It is a free web application that educators can use to create effective online learning sites. One of its main advantages is its open source, or has open source allowing any user with programming Knowledge to modify and adapt the environment according to their own needs. Moodle was created by Martin Dougiamas in 2002. In the beginning the “M” on Moodle acronym was the first letter of Dougiamas name, Martin. Dougiamas developed Moodle to help educators create online courses with a focus on interaction and collaborative construction of content.

Uses of Moodle

- Moodle can be developed for large organizations or for a primary school or education enthusiast.
- Moodle used for full online courses or to augment face-to-face learning (hybrid or blended learning)
- Moodle of activity modules such as forums, databases, and wikis to build richly collaborative communities
- Moodle being content to students and assess learning through online quizzes and tests.

General Features of the Moodle Platform

Role	Function
Administrator	Manages the whole environment
Teacher	Generate events, courses or subjects according to the thematic areas defined Generate training or events which are designated
Student	Accesses and interacts with a specific event and participates in the subjects they are subscribed

Moodle the World’s Best LMS

There is top three benefits that are become Moodle the world’s bes

1. Open Source and Free

Moodle LMS itself is free, because it is open source software distributed under the GNU General Public License. In less technical terms, this means that users and organizations have the freedom to run, study, share, and modify the software to meet their unique needs. While some Moodle site owners choose to support Moodle completely on their own, others outsource specific tasks to Moodle Service Providers because it more cost-effective.

2. Supported by A Global Community

One of the reasons why Moodle is the world’s best LMS is because it supported by a global community of developers. A large benefit of open-source software is that the code is open for scrutiny. This means that developers from all over the world can access the code, and modify it so that it is more secure. It also means that the code is scrutinized by actual Moodle users. The benefit of this is that Moodle is constantly being updated by people who understand what users need for better user experience.

3. Configurable, Highly-Flexible and Feature-Rich

The leading reason why organizations love Moodle is largely because it is configurable, highly-flexible and feature-rich. On top of being able to modify Moodle’s open source code, there are hundreds of Moodle Plugins that allow you to configure Moodle so it performs just the way you like. With over 500 Moodle plugins developed by the global community, your learners, managers and administrators have the opportunity to flourish in an environment that makes learning collaborative, engaging and fun?

Moodle in Education and Training

Although initially designed for higher education environment (university), Moodle has quickly become used across a broad range of organisations worldwide to conduct courses fully online or support face-to-face teaching and learning.

Its modularity, flexibility, security and free availability have attracted learning communities ranging from single primary school classrooms to large universities, businesses, government departments and other places where people learn.

Moodle Used for in Education

Flexible Learning

Moodle’s eLearning platform allows for face to face, video conferencing, 24/7 access to courses and content. Materials can be accessed from anywhere learners have Internet access, giving them the freedom to learn on their own time. Online learning allows students to better balance work with school, as students are able to learn when they can, not when they must.

Blended Learning

Mixing in-class sessions with online learning for an engaging learning experience that keeps learners stimulated through various avenues of learning.

Multilingual

Moodle can be translated in over 100 languages, making it inclusive for learners across the globe. This allows to quality up to date learning.

Mobile Compatibility

Moodle offers mobile eLearning, making learning-on-the-go easier. Mobile eLearning is considered a complementary aspect of the learning process, providing greater flexibility for learners to access course materials on any mobile device.

Engaging Learners

Keeping learners interested and excited with mixed learning methods, as well as a customized learning experience thanks to the 250 + Moodle plugins available.

Teacher uses for Moodle

1. Post documents for students
2. Post relevant web links on topics
3. Initiate web conversations via forum
4. Collect assignments
5. Electronic assessments
6. Create online courses
7. Upload forums
8. Create online tests and examinations
9. Divide students files and lessons Open into classes
10. Chat sessions

Student uses for Moodle

1. Allows students to have one-on-one with teacher
2. Online chat room for discussions
3. Group collaboration via integrated wiki
4. Safe environment for communication compared to other social networks
5. Follow the lessons
6. Upload their homework and test
7. Chat sessions
8. Take part into forums

Conclusion

Moodle is one of the most user friendly and affordable innovative strategies because when Moodle is used appropriately, it can stimulate students' interest and motivation to be actively engaged in their educational experience. Moodle allows students to have an opportunity to participate actively in the course beyond the limits of the official class hours and classroom. Moodle also helps to positively moderate the competition to "succeed as an individual" that often manifests among learners and instead it fosters collaborative learning through its capacity to support group learning. The abilities of Moodle such as increasing access to the course, supporting shared creation, collaboration and mastery of knowledge are very essential in any university learning environment. The cooperative learning that evolves through the interactive nature of online resources such Moodle, promote higher student achievement, self-reliance, collaborative culture and lifelong learning skills.

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